

A Framework for Integrating Domain Knowledge & Deep Learning for 3D Shape Analysis of Lithic Fragments

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Abstract

The increasing volume of data available for archaeological analysis requires automation, and advances in machine learning and artificial intelligence are being deployed to meet these needs. Deep learning approaches, in particular have been very successful in many areas. These methods, however, are something of a 'black box' – while they successfully map from input data to the desired output, they are difficult to interpret. Related to this is the fact that they perform best when trained 'end-to-end' which makes incorporating expert knowledge into them difficult.

In this paper we propose a new direction, incorporating more explicit reasoning into deep learning systems for fine-grained 3D shape analysis. Our target application is the analysis of lithic flakes from pre-contact Māori stone tool manufacture. As well as having significant archaeological interest, this application exemplifies some of the challenges of fine-grained shape analysis. While our work is at an early stage, we believe that the overall approach may be of interest to other members of the community as they explore how to use deep learning to solve archaeological problems.

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Introduction

Advances in machine learning and artificial intelligence, and deep learning approaches in particular, have revolutionised many areas of analysis. These methods, however, are often quite opaque – they learn a mapping from the input data to the desired output, but are something of a black box. This raises challenges when incorporating expert knowledge about the process into a deep learning system. This is of particular concern when there are social or cultural aspects at play, as is often the case in archaeological and historical contexts. In this paper we propose an approach that allows us to open up the black box, at least in places, and insert more explicit reasoning, for the fine-grained analysis of 3D shape. In particular we target the analysis of lithic flakes from pre-contact Māori stone tool manufacture, such as those shown in [Figure 1](#). Whether historically recovered through archaeological excavation or surface collections gathered by community, individual artefacts in legacy lithic collections often lack description limiting their contribution to research without first addressing extensive cataloguing processes. Both for these, and the volume of lithics newly recovered from current excavations, this application is both of great archaeological interest, and provides an ideal test-case for the shape analysis network.

Figure 1 – Part of a donation as received by Tūhura Otago Museum of lithic artefacts from North Otago.

Deep Learning and Implicit Layers

Since the success of AlexNet (Krizhevsky et al., 2012) for object recognition in images in 2012, deep neural networks have come to dominate many areas of computing. The essential idea of these approaches is that many layers of simple computational units (LeCun et al., 2015) can be combined to learn complex patterns from training data ([Figure 2](#), left). These simple units, or artificial neurons, compute weighted sums of the input from previous layers, and these weights are adjusted to learn to perform a given task. During training, example data is presented to the network and the output compared with the desired (ground truth) result. Correct results can be reinforced and mistakes corrected through a process of back-propagation (Rumelhart et al.,

26 1986), which is essentially an application of the chain rule to adjust the network weights by
 27 gradient descent or some other optimisation approach.

Figure 2 – Deep neural networks are trained through back-propagation, where derivatives are used to adjust weights based on training data (left). It has often been observed that a single network that is trained ‘end-to-end’ (middle, top) is more effective than dividing the process into discrete stages (middle bottom). This makes it difficult to integrate knowledge into the networks, but implicit layers (right) allow optimisation algorithms to be incorporated into an end-to-end training scheme as long as a derivative is available.

28 It has been observed that training such networks ‘end-to-end’ as a single optimisation process
 29 is much more effective than dividing the task into a pipeline of smaller operations (Figure 2,
 30 middle). This makes it difficult to apply prior knowledge to the optimisation process or to inter-
 31rogate intermediate stages in the solution, as the network becomes a monolithic black-box.

32 Recently there has been great interest in the machine learning and artificial intelligence com-
 33munities in integrating explicit algorithms into the deep learning process (Figure 2, right). There
 34are a wide range of methods, but the general approach is to ensure that a derivative can be com-
 35puted for the explicit algorithm, enabling error signals to pass across when training the network.
 36This approach goes by many names, such as differentiable layers (Agrawal et al., 2019), implicit
 37layers (Geng et al., 2021), and deep declarative networks (Gould et al., 2021). In deep declara-
 38tive networks, for example, explicit reasoning can be wrapped inside a ‘declarative node’, which
 39can then be inserted into an artificial neural network. The standard neural network training ap-
 40proaches then learn to provide the appropriate input to the declarative node so that it produces
 41the desired output.

42 Lithic Analysis

43 We are interested in applying these implicit or declarative approaches to fine-grained 3D
 44shape analysis. In particular, we are investigating lithic analysis of waste flakes formed during
 45the manufacture of tōki (stone adzes). Adze working flakes are a key element of archaeological
 46analysis (Andrefsky Jr, 1998) and can provide a wealth of otherwise inaccessible information
 47on early Māori industry, trade, and production systems. Together with a lack of non-shape cues
 48such as visual texture, this makes for a challenging classification task, but one where domain
 49knowledge could be effectively employed.

50 In particular, each flake is formed by a sharp tap to a flat part of the tool being formed – the
 51striking platform. This causes a shock-wave to pass through the stone, creating a distinctive bulb
 52of percussion. If skilfully struck, this shock-wave forms a clean flake, with a sharp, uniform edge.
 53Since these flakes have little visual texture detail, 3D shape is the sole cue for identifying these
 54features. Measuring these properties gives us important information about the manufacture of

Figure 3 – 3D scans of a small assemblage of flakes from the experimental archaeology manufacture of a preform (top left). Note that while all share common characteristics of interest, their overall size, aspect ratio, etc. vary greatly.

55 these tools, but hundreds of flakes are produced in the production of a single tool. Automating
 56 the description and classification process, therefore, will require the integration of deep learning
 57 with domain-specific knowledge to allow interpretable and robust analysis.

58

Methodology

59 As an example of how this might work, consider the pipeline shown in [Figure 4](#). In this case
 60 we consider the task of labelling the key parts of a flake produced during stone tool manufacture.
 61 There are two main stages to this process – segmenting the flake into its components, and then
 62 labelling each part. While neural networks are effective at both segmentation and labelling tasks,
 63 there are elements of this task that we believe could benefit from other approaches, so we pro-
 64 pose a mix of explicit algorithms (orange boxes) and learned features from neural networks (blue).
 65 These explicit algorithms can then be designed or adapted to incorporate expert knowledge.

Figure 4 – A potential pipeline for segmenting and labelling parts of a stone flake, integrating explicit algorithms (orange) where domain knowledge can be introduced with deep learning (blue).

66 For the segmentation phase, neural networks have been very effective at labelling sub-parts
 67 of objects (Mo et al., 2019a). These approaches, however, typically label each point individually
 68 and so do not enforce spatial continuity. As a result, individual points may be mislabelled, despite
 69 their neighbours being correctly labelled. Furthermore, the parts of a stone flake that are of
 70 interested are often separated by clear geometric features, such as the ridges between fracture

71 planes. This knowledge could be used to influence a neural network through providing it as
72 additional input data, adding a loss function to encourage its use, etc., but these approaches are
73 indirect and influence rather than constrain the solution. We propose to include graph-based
74 segmentation algorithms (e.g. Shi and Malik, 2000) into the network to address these issues.

75 Labelling object parts is often done alongside segmentation in neural networks, but again
76 we believe there are benefits to using a more explicit methods here. Firstly, separating the two
77 components would allow us to use an over-segmentation of the object then group the segments
78 into semantic parts. Such approaches have been effective in image processing (Barcelos et al.,
79 2024). Secondly, neighbourhood relations could be exploited to encode domain knowledge, such
80 as the fact that the striking platform is adjacent and perpendicular to the curved facet caused
81 by the bulb of percussion. These can be incorporated via collaborative clustering (Chakraborti
82 et al., 2017, 2020) or graph-based approaches.

83 One advantage of this approach is that the entire system can be trained 'end-to-end'. That
84 means that the early stage feature extraction used for segmentation can be chosen in order to
85 ensure that the segments that are produced are suitable for the later processing stages (labelling
86 in our example). More importantly, it allows us to use machine learning when appropriate, while
87 still retaining the benefits of more explicit reasoning when we can. This provides a clearer under-
88 standing of what computation is being performed, allowing us to incorporate domain knowledge
89 into the system.

90 We are in the initial stages of implementing a demonstrator of the approach we propose.
91 For the first steps we are developing segmentation and labelling methods in the declarative
92 network framework on generic 3D shape analysis benchmarks (Mo et al., 2019b). However, the
93 archaeological application is an ideal test for more nuanced shape analysis. The flakes formed
94 during stone tool manufacture have complex but patterned shape characteristics (Andrefsky Jr,
95 1998), but these can be obscured by gross variation in overall shape.

96 Conclusion

97 The machine learning revolution will have a significant impact on all areas of research. There
98 is, however, a growing realisation that the incorporation of domain knowledge into these systems
99 is necessary to produce reliable systems that can explain as well as compute. In this work we are
100 exploring this in the context of fine-grained 3D shape analysis, combining graph algorithms and
101 statistical techniques with deep learning to address this problem.

102 Analysis of Māori stone tool manufacture provides both a concrete context in which to test
103 our theoretical advances and the ability to contribute to an application of specific importance
104 to Aotearoa's culture, hertiage, and history. Beyond this application, we believe that the general
105 approach of incorporating expertise through explicit, expert-informed algorithms into deep net-
106 works allows us to have the best of both worlds. We can learn to extract features from large
107 datasets automatically, while still understanding the analysis that is made on the basis of those
108 features.

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Conflict of interest disclosure

119 Authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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